

"MICROPROPAGATION STUDIES IN BAMBOO (*Bambusa balcooa*)"

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Abstract

Bamboos represent one of the world's most important natural and renewable bioresources and are among the most useful plants known to mankind. They are most productive and fastest growing species on the planet. It covers about 37 million hectares which is just about 1% of the forest worldwide. Bamboo has several advantages in terms of sustainability and carbon fixing capacity compared to the other fast-growing species. It can play a significant role in linking climate change mitigation to sustainable development of the world. This communication describes for an efficient protocol for large scale production of *Bambusa balcooa*.

Shoot initiation & establishment from nodal explant on different BAP concentration (1.0,2.0,3.0,5.0 mg/l BAP) was successfully done. The best shoot length (average shoot length 1.8 ± 0.11 cm) was observed on media containing 2.0mg/l BAP.

Keywords: *Bambusa balcooa*, Nodal segment, Micropropagation, BAP, NAA, IBA.

Introduction:

Plant tissue culture technology is being widely used for large-scale plant multiplication. The commercial technology is primarily based on micropropagation. In which rapid proliferation is achieved from tiny stem cuttings.

Bamboos are a group of evergreen perennial grasses belonging to family - Poaceae and sub-family - Bambusoideae. There are about 88 genera and 1400 species of bamboos distributed worldwide covering an area of more than 14 million hectares with 80% of species and area under bamboos confined to south and south-east Asia, largely in China, India and Myanmar. Bamboos are having largest use in paper and pulp industry (Varmah and Pant, 1981) and in India, it constitutes nearly 70% of the raw material for this industry (Rout and Das, 1994).

Bamboos are conventionally propagated through seeds and vegetative propagation through offsets, rhizomes and culm cuttings. But both these methods are beset with many problems which restrict their large-scale multiplication. Traditional method of vegetative propagation by culm cuttings, offsets and rhizomes limits the number of propagules and again it is slow, cumbersome and labour-intensive procedure and hence, inadequate for large scale establishment of bamboo plantations. *Bambusa balcooa* grows best at lower altitudes: above 1000 m altitude stems become smaller in length and diameter. It thrives under a wide range of moisture and soil conditions, growing in almost permanently humid conditions along rivers and lakes, but also in areas with a severe dry season, where the plants may become completely defoliated.

Material and Methods:**Collection of Plant material:**

10-15 cm nodal segments of bamboo (*Bambusa balcooa*) were collected from campus of College of Agriculture, Loni Pravara-413637, Survey no. 361.

Plate 2.1 Collection of Bamboo Explants

Explant used:

Nodal segments of bamboo were used as explants.

Methods:**Media preparation:**

According to the available literature on in vitro propagation of Bamboo Murashige and Skoog's (1962) medium is the most used growing medium for Bamboo the procedure for preparation of media is as follows

1. The medium was prepared by adding 13 gm MS media and final volume was made up with distilled water. The P^H is adjusted to 5.7.
2. Agar was used for solidifying the medium.
3. Media was heated in microwave for dissolving the agar
4. Then autoclaved at 121°C for 20 min. at 15 psi pressure.
5. The media was poured into washed culture bottles in LAF.
6. Media transferred to the media storage room where they were kept under aseptic condition for solidification.

2.3.2 Initiation stage:**2.3.2.1 Surface sterilization:**

1. Explants were selected (nodal segments)
2. Explants were cut into optimum size (3-4 cm)
3. Explants were washed under running tap water (5-8 times)
4. Explants treated with tween-80 for 5 min
5. Explants were washed under running tap water (for 30 min.)
6. Treated with 0.1% Bavistin for 15 min
7. Explants were washed under running tap water (for 30 min.)
8. Again, treated with 0.1% Bavistin for 15 min.
9. Treated with of 70% ethanol for 30 sec. in LAF.
10. Explants were washed with D.W. (5-6 times).
11. Treated of 0.1% HgCl₂ for 5 min in LAF.
12. Explants were thoroughly washed with sterile D.W. (for 5-6 times)

Inoculation of explants:

All inoculations and aseptic manipulations were carried out in a laminar air flow cabinet. Before use, the working surface of the laminar air flow cabinet was cleaned by swabbing with 70% ethyl alcohol and switch on the UV light for 20 min. to reduce the chances of contamination. After that the UV light became switched "off" and switch "on" the ordinary light.

Table no.2.1 Media combinations for Initiation

Sr. No.	Medium+ Hormones
1.	MS medium
2.	MS + 1.0 mg/l BAP
3.	MS + 2.0 mg/l BAP
4.	MS + 3.0 mg/l BAP
5.	MS + 5.0 mg/l BAP

Culture incubation:

The inoculated culture bottles were inoculated at 25 ± 2 °C temperature for 16 hours light and 8 hours dark per day in 2000 Lux light intensity under cool fluorescent white light in the culture room. Data were recorded in terms of average shoots length (cm), average number of shoots per explant.

Result and Discussion:**Culture Initiation:**

Treatment with 0.1% HgCl₂ did improve the frequency of aseptic cultures without adversely affecting the overall frequency of the bud

break. Considering the incidence of browning and the frequency of the bud break, 0.1% HgCl₂ for 10 min. was regarded as the best treatment to initiate aseptic cultures of nodal segments from the mature plants.

Table no.3.1 Observations for establishment of bamboo explants using different media conc. after 5-6 weeks of culture.

Sr. No.	Medium + Hormones	Average shoot length (in cm) mean±SE	% Survival
1.	MS medium	1±0.41	50
2.	MS + 1.0 mg/l BAP	1.4±0.2	60
3.	MS + 2.0 mg/l BAP	1.8±0.11	80
4.	MS + 3.0 mg/l BAP	1.6±0.30	75
5.	MS + 5.0 mg/l BAP	1.5±0.15	70

Plate no.3.1 Result of Initiation of Bamboo plant**Discussion:**

Shoot initiation and establishment from *Bambusa balcooa* nodal explants are cultured on MS basal and MS supplemented with different concentration of growth hormones. BAP 0.5mg/l, 1.0mg/l, 2.0mg/l, 3.0mg/l, 5.0mg/l was successfully used.

Data were obtained after 5 weeks of initiation of culture showed that nodal segments of *Bambusa balcooa* could be established at all tested media including the control medium (free from growth regulators). The best results were obtained on MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mg/l BAP.

Summary And Conclusion:**Summary:**

Bamboo shoots are greatly demanded in the international market for their shoot-based food industry. The productions of large numbers of bambooplants were possible through micropropagation technique. In bamboo MS medium containing 2.0 mg/l BAP was the best for culture initiation. (Average shoot length 1.8±0.11 cm).

Conclusion:

Plant tissue culture is the important and new advanced technique in the agriculture sector, and now used in large extent throughout the world to get the superior quality and quantity of the crop from shoot meristem, root meristem, leaf disc, shoot tip explant to get the homozygous plant having similar properties like pre-existing plant.

In vitro bud break was enhanced by supplementation of BAP.

In MS medium containing 2.0 mg/l BAP was the best for culture initiation. The best shoot length (average shoot length 1.8±0.11 cm) was observed on media containing 2.0 mg/l BAP.

References

1. **Anand, M., Brar, J., and Sood, A. 2013.** Invitro propagation of an edible bamboo *Bambusa bambos* and assessment of clonal fluidity through molecular markers. *Journal of Medical and Bioengineering*. 2(4): 257-261.
2. **Ansari, I., Gupta, S., Soni, S., and Baig, A. 2017.** In vitro regeneration of *Bambusa balcooa* (Bamboo) through nodal segments. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 6(10): 4901-4905.
3. **Choudhary, A. K., Ranjan, A., and Kumari, P. 2016.** In vitro shoot proliferation for rapid and mass production of quality planting materials of *Bambusa nutans* in the climatic conditions of Bihar, India. *Indian J. Energy*. 5(2): 1-11.
4. **Das, M., and Pal, A. 2005.** Clonal propagation and production of genetically uniform regenerants from axillary meristems of adult bamboo. *J. Plant Biochem. Biotechnol.* 14: 185-188.
5. **Murashige, T., and Skoog, F. 1962.** A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassa with tobacco tissue culture. *Physiol. Plant.* 15: 473-497.
6. **Ray, S. S., and Ali, M. N. 2016.** Factors influencing micropropagation of bamboo species using nodal explants: A Review. *Res. J. Pharm. Biol. Chem. Sci.* 7(5): 2877-2888.
7. **Rout, G. R., and Das, P. 1994.** Somatic embryogenesis and in vitro flowering of three species of bamboos. *Plant Cell Rep.* 13: 683-686.